

Proton catalyzed amino-Claisen rearrangement : A practical one step approach to the synthesis of 2-allylarylamines from *N*-allylarylamines

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Abstract : Proton catalyzed amino-Claisen rearrangement of *N*-allylarylamines (**1a-h**) afforded 2-allylarylamines (**2a-h**) respectively in moderate to good yields.

Keywords : 2-Allylarylamines, Claisen rearrangement, proton catalysis.

The Claisen rearrangement is important in view of its synthetic utility and mechanistic aspects^{1,2}. The analogous amino-Claisen rearrangement too provides similar unique synthetic opportunities but it is considerably less facile than its oxygen counterpart. It appears that the drastic conditions required in aza series tend to produce products in low yields¹⁻⁵. Therefore, only a few examples of amino-Claisen rearrangement of arylamines are known in the literature.

2-Allylarylamines which result from the amino-Claisen rearrangement of *N*-allylarylamines are important precursors in palladium induced heteroannulation to give indoles⁶. In a quest to examine the feasibility of other amine substrates in indole synthesis, we required a variety of 2-allylarylamines (**2a-h**). The amino-Claisen rearrangement of *N*-allylarylamines (**1a-h**) appeared a most simple and convenient method for its synthesis. Our initial attempt to obtain **2** from **1** through the amino-Claisen rearrangement using an uncatalyzed thermal reaction conditions was unsuccessful. Hence, the use of the catalyst seemed inevitable in effecting the thermally difficult reactions. In accord to the earlier procedures, which used protic acid catalysis in conventional Claisen rearrangements of oxygen analogues, we thought it worthwhile to examine H₂SO₄ and TFA to facilitate this reaction⁷ in the present work. To our knowledge, there has been only one reported method which used these catalysts in amino-Claisen rearrangement⁸. The use of these catalysts

in amino-Claisen rearrangement of *N*-allylarylamines (**1a-h**) in H₂SO₄ or TFA gave 2-allylaryl-amines (**2a-h**) in good yields (Table 1). The results which have emanated from this study are summarized in this paper.

Results and discussion

The protic acid 2 *N* H₂SO₄ and trifluoroacetic acid/water/dioxan (2/1/1, v/v) (TWD) were used as catalysts in the rearrangement of a series of *N*-allylarylamines (**1a-h**). In a typical run, *N*-allylarylamines (**1a-h**) was heated at 170–190 °C with 2 *N* H₂SO₄ or TWD for 25 min which furnished *o*-allylarylamines (**2a-h**) in yields ranging from 38–53%.

Our results corroborate to the earlier observations made on the rearrangement of protic acid salts of *N*-allylarylamine (**1**) which has been shown to proceed under relatively mild conditions than the uncatalyzed neat reactions⁸. However, there has been a limitation to this method that in some cases it produced products of unknown identity. It has been suggested that the hydration of allyl chain probably occurred during the rearrangement which formed the side products. Comparable results were obtained with TWD but the amount of unidentified products was large in this reaction (Table 1).

The results of our study demonstrate that proton catalyzed rearrangement tolerated a variety of substituents in

Table 1. Conversion of *N*-allylarylamines (1a-h) to *o*-allylarylamines (2a-h)

Substrate	Product ^a	Yield (%)	
		2 N H ₂ SO ₄	TWD
	53	48	
	50	44	
	46	40	
	43	38	
	51	50	
	40	42	
	48	40	
	50	43	

^aProducts were fully characterized by elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectral data

the substrate and the reaction was relatively slow with electron withdrawing substituents. Similar results were observed on the conventional Claisen rearrangement of oxygen analogues in the literature^{7,9-11}.

All the products **2a-h** are characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR (Table 2) as well as by direct comparison with authentic samples **2a**, **2e**, **2g-h** prepared through known routes¹²⁻¹⁵.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Pye Unicam Model SP3-300 infracord in neat and on KBr pellets. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a FT NMR Bruker AM 300L spectrometer using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent and TMS as an internal reference. All *N*-allylarylamines (**1a-h**) were prepared by the method reported previously¹⁶.

General procedure for amino-Claisen rearrangement of N-allylarylamines (1a-h) :

(a) In 2 N H₂SO₄ :

A mixture of *N*-allylarylamine (**1a-h**, 11.25 mmol) and 2 N H₂SO₄ (35 ml) was heated at 170–190 °C for 25 min. It was made alkaline with NaHCO₃ solution, extracted with Et₂O (3 × 20 ml), dried on MgSO₄ and concentrated. The crude product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel with hexane-ethyl acetate (10 : 1) to give *o*-allylarylamines **2a-b** and **2d-h** as oils and **2c** as white solid (yields 40–53%, Table 1); **2c**, m.p. 148–149 °C.

(b) In TWD :

A mixture of *N*-allylarylamine (**1a-h**, 11.25 mmol) and TWD (35 ml) was heated at 170–190 °C for 25 min. It was made alkaline with NaHCO₃ solution, extracted with Et₂O (3 × 20 ml), dried on MgSO₄ and concentrated. The crude product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel with hexane-ethyl acetate (10 : 1) to give *o*-allylarylamines **2a-b** and **2d-h** as oils and **2c** as white solid (yields 40–50%, Table 1); **2c**, m.p. 148–149 °C.

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Table 2. Spectroscopic data of the *o*-allylarylaminines (2a-h)

Product	IR (cm^{-1})	^1H NMR (δ , ppm)	^{13}C NMR (δ , ppm)
2a	3468, 3380, 2920, 2850, 1630, 1620, 1580, 999, 914	6.96–6.72 (2H, m, ArH), 6.58 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.05–5.60 (1H, m, =CH=), 5.20–4.90 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3.32 (2H, br.s, NH ₂), 3.14 (2H, d, J 6.5 Hz, –CH ₂ –), 2.06 (3H, s, CH ₃)	147.23, 136.42, 130.38, 126.74, 124.67, 116.16, 118.85, 116.32, 36.76, 21.11
2b	3452, 3380, 2930, 2840, 1618, 1514, 1450, 990, 920	6.80–6.60 (3H, m, ArH), 6.00–5.86 (1H, m, =CH=), 5.12–5.04 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3.81–3.78 (5H, m, NH ₂ , OCH ₃), 3.32–3.28 (2H, m, –CH ₂ –)	145.86, 134.37, 124.06, 120.09, 117.64, 115.20, 132.71, 111.44, 55.54, 36.16
2c	3430–3200, 2970, 2860, 1660, 1632, 1628, 1512, 990, 922	7.52–6.92 (3H, m, ArH), 6.03–5.86 (5H, m, =CH=, CONH ₂ , NH ₂), 5.19–5.10 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3.30 (2H, J 6.1 Hz, –CH ₂ –)	174.62, 147.78, 137.46, 134.68, 131.96, 119.92, 117.38, 118.22, 165.67, 36.83
2d	3485, 3375, 2950, 2850, 1695, 1622, 1589, 1575, 990, 918	7.83–7.79 (1H, dd, J 1.7, 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.19–7.16 (1H, dd, J 1.6, 8.2 Hz, ArH), 6.63 (1H, dd, J 7.3, 8.2 Hz, ArH), 6.01–5.86 (3H, m, NH ₂ , =CH=), 5.16–5.07 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 4.40 (2H, q, J 8.0 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.32 (2H, dd, J 1.8, 6.3 Hz, –CH ₂ –), 1.30 (3H, t, J 8.0 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃)	169.50, 150.15, 135.65, 127.32, 130.28, 122.26, 116.40, 118.40, 112.45, 60.23, 36.82, 12.25
2e	3350, 3240–2830, 1610, 1623, 1559, 1430, 996, 920	6.67–6.62 (3H, m, ArH), 6.03–5.90 (1H, m, =CH=), 5.15–5.07 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3.36 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, –CH ₂ –), 3.34 (4H, br.s, 2NH ₂)	135.59, 133.96, 124.81, 122.40, 119.86, 116.89, 116.48, 115.96, 37.18
2f	3458, 3380, 2960, 2850, 1622, 1610, 1575, 1440, 990, 921	7.01 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz, ArH), 6.72 (1H, dd, J 2.3, 8.2 Hz, ArH), 6.32 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, ArH), 6.02–5.89 (1H, m, =CH=), 5.15–5.07 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3.73 (2H, s, NH ₂), 3.37 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, –CH ₂ –)	146.45, 137.16, 131.72, 131.50, 129.60, 122.36, 120.49, 117.10, 114.65, 36.65
2g	3460, 3382, 2976, 2856, 1628, 1620, 1582, 995, 920	7.02–6.97 (2H, m, ArH), 6.62 (1H, dd, J 9.1, 3.0 Hz, ArH), 5.97–5.87 (1H, m, =CH=), 5.17–5.09 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3.81 (2H, s, NH ₂), 3.27 (2H, d, J 6.2 Hz, –CH ₂ –)	143.78, 134.68, 130.20, 128.0, 125.76, 124.92, 117.35, 114.80, 36.67
2h	3458, 3379, 2976, 2860, 1625, 1602, 1518, 1490, 990, 918	7.74–7.06 (6H, m, ArH), 6.03–5.89 (1H, m, =CH=), 5.16–5.03 (2H, m, =CH ₂), 3.48 (4H, m, –CH ₂ –, NH ₂)	147.32, 137.12, 134.89, 129.98, 128.10, 127.29, 126.10, 123.18, 117.68, 116.68, 36.80

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